

How much does your digital model weigh? Introducing embodied carbon to beginning-design students in architecture

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Abstract

We describe a simple Rhino-based method for introducing embodied-carbon analysis in early design stages. The method produces visualizations comparing the relative quantity of materials, and estimates per-material weights to calculate the overall (simulated) weight of Rhino models. We position our method as a means of introducing architecture students to embodied-carbon concepts and digital modeling practices.

The context of embodied carbon

In our capacity as educators in a professional architecture degree program, we are interested in presenting an approach to professional practice wherein architects are commissioned to reconfigure existing buildings for improved performance. By “performance,” we mean enhancing the quality of an existing building’s function, comfort, and overall experience, and reducing its operational and embodied carbon footprints. Our immediate-term goals are to heighten student awareness of embodied-carbon concepts, and to emphasize their roles as beginning designers in having a measurable impact through early-stage design decisions. This includes introducing concepts of embodied carbon, and particularly its potential impacts and effects, at a fundamental level. The method we describe here is aimed to heighten student awareness of embodied carbon in design projects by using volume and weight as proxies. We expect that the exercise will prompt students to develop questions requiring greater precision as their design education progresses. In this way, we hope to have a triggering effect on student habits of thought, similar to that of Buckminster Fuller’s question “how much does your building weigh?” (Zung 2001)

We use the term embodied carbon to refer to the total carbon equivalent (CO_{2e}) associated with constructing and maintaining a building during production, construction, operation (except utilities), and demolition and disposal, i. e., life-cycle embodied carbon (Hu and Efram 2021; De Wolf et al. 2017). Embodied carbon represents a significant share of existing buildings’ contribution to global carbon emissions, with estimates of that contribution ranging from

25% to 75% of the total (International Energy Agency 2019; Pomponi and Moncaster 2016). Addressing this situation will require improvements to existing buildings’ energy efficiency to reduce operational carbon, and finding ways to leverage or utilize buildings’ embodied carbon as resources or for carbon sequestration (Elefante 2023; Lin et al. 2022; Gerfen 2020). For example, Far and Far (2019) suggest thermal-retrofit changes to the building envelope; Khadra et al. (2020) address modifications to installed HVAC systems; Paone and Bacher (2018) explore the potentials on occupant behavior changes; and Ruparathna et al. (2016) demonstrate the potential for such modifications to result in improved energy efficiency of existing buildings.

Following Bragança et al. (2014), Attia et al. (2012), and Kohler and Moffatt (2003), we assume that early-stage design decisions will be more impactful on life-cycle carbon costs than later-stage decisions.

The context of the studio

Our work is situated in a semester-long design studio, under our joint direction, in the professional Master of Architecture (M. Arch.) program at the University of Minnesota. Depending on individual students’ undergraduate background, they enroll in the studio in either the first or second year of their graduate education (University of Minnesota 2023). The studio, which introduces students to design-decision processes related to environmental technology and high-performance regenerative practices, is divided into two half-semester modules: “Net Positive Design,” in the first half, and “Integrated Design” in the second. The Net Positive pedagogy is informed by Mang and Reed (2015), who refer to net positive buildings as those that “add value” to ecological systems and generate more energy than they require to meet their own needs. The Integrated Design approach is aimed at educating students in the decision-making processes involved in integrating “building envelope systems and assemblies, structural systems, environmental control systems, life safety systems, and the measurable outcomes of building performance” (National Architectural Accrediting Board 2020).

In a typical academic year, a section of the studio enrolls nine to twelve students. The student groups remain intact for the duration of the semester. Each group is led by two instructors, one of whom has the primary responsibility for teaching Net Positive Design in the semester's first half, and the other for teaching Integrated Design in the second half. While sharing a unified, cohort-wide schedule (including attending common lectures, consultant workshops, and energy modeling training) each studio group has a distinct project. In Spring 2023, as studio co-instructors, we worked with one group of ten graduate students. In practice we equally shared responsibility for teaching Net Positive Design and Integrated Design.

The Net Positive studio was first implemented in our institution by our colleagues Mary Guzowski and Richard Graves, drawing inspiration from Mang and Reed's approach (Srivastava 2020). While the Net Positive studio emphasizes iterative modeling of net zero performance aligned with Architecture 2030 goals, net zero is only a part of the studio's agenda. In general, the studio engages a broad range of approaches to achieving net-positive impact, including biophilic design (Guzowski 2015; Guzowski 2022). Our approach to net-positive impact involved developing approaches to overall carbon reduction while emphasizing cognitive diversity. As a way of promoting "sustainable, resilient, and inclusive design," we assigned our students principles from the AIA Framework for Design Excellence (American Institute of Architects 2023). And as we have done elsewhere, we asked our students to establish cooperative work arrangements, exchanging drawings and models, and sharing concepts and skills for teaching and learning (Srivastava and Christenson 2021). In doing so, we hoped to promote "shifting allegiances" to ideas and concepts as they evolve over the course of the semester (Srivastava 2020).

Our studio brief required students to materially transform Nolte Center, an existing three-story building in Minneapolis, originally constructed in 1936 (Fig. 1). Rather than focusing the brief on a specific program, students could choose to either work with the building's current functions (university offices, classrooms, and study spaces), or to suggest alternative uses. We emphasized the potential to create a cold-climate courtyard.

Fig. 1. Nolte Center, University of Minnesota

We proposed to our students that the existing building could be regarded as a "congealed repository" of matter (material) and effort (labor and energy), capable of transformation into a mechanism of net positive impact. More specifically, we asked students to situate proposals for transformation relative to three strategic extremes: reincarnation (referring to the possibility of completely disassembling the existing building and reassembling a new building using the same materials), reconfiguration (referring to the possibility of adding volume within or atop the existing building), and as-is (referring to the possibility of leaving the existing building materially unchanged but transformed in other ways, e. g., operationally or behaviorally).

We assigned each student a discrete segment of the building, through which they conducted research, observation, and documentation. This process enabled a comprehensive understanding of the entire structure through a deep comprehension of its individual components. Students explored and investigate the building through a combination-drawing and combination-making method. They taught each other what they learned from the deep examination of their assigned segment.

Through the lenses of students' individual efforts, we expected them to second-guess and critique the design decisions that led to the building's construction and operation over its lifespan. We aimed to familiarize students with building science principles, systems, and performance frameworks, all within an overall framework of "Net Positive Design" and "Integrated Design."

Embodied carbon in beginning design education

Students in this studio may be encountering embodied-carbon concepts for the first time. In 2023, roughly half of

our students held undergraduate degrees in non-architecture fields. Similarly, students may be new to the idea of working with digital models as design tools, and parametric tools such as Grasshopper may be completely unfamiliar. In 2023, in response to a questionnaire, three out of ten students “strongly agreed” that they were familiar with Rhino as a design tool, while only one of the ten indicated the same level of familiarity with Grasshopper.

Digital tools can provide early-stage embodied carbon analysis (Alwan and Jones 2022; Cucuzza et al. 2022). Several popular tools exist for visualizing embodied carbon impacts, including EC3, Athena Impact Estimator, and the Tally Carbon Calculator (Yan et al. 2022). Building Information Modeling (BIM) and its connections to Life-Cycle Analysis (LCA) are frequently discussed in the literature (Farid Mohajer and Aksamija 2019). By examining LCA with the support of BIM, students can engage with sustainability assessments and incorporate them into their decision-making processes more readily (Gomes et al. 2022). We contend that parametric methods in general, and Grasshopper in particular, hold unique promise for beginning-design students. Customized parametric methods offer reliable techniques for interrogating digital models, e. g., involving the use of Dynamo (Hollberg, Genova, and Habert 2020) or Grasshopper (Hollberg et al. 2016). Moreover, custom parametric methods can make it possible for “non-experts [to] apply LCA during the design phase without much additional effort” (Hollberg et al. 2016).

Methods.

In this section of our paper, we consider the technical aspects of our method for assessing a digital model of an evolving design project in terms of material volume and (simulated) weight. We begin by considering the example of Nolte Center, the building our students examined in 2023. We constructed a Rhino model of Nolte Center model for our students’ use (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Digital model of Nolte Center

For any Rhino model to be valid for our method, we require that two specific conditions be satisfied: first, that entities within the model are constructed as “closed polysurfaces” for which Rhino can calculate volume properties; and second, that each of the closed polysurfaces is assigned to a layer (i. e., a category) corresponding to a specific building material, ideally a material for which an approximate unit weight is known. Our model satisfies both conditions.

Our method relies on the use of Grasshopper within Rhino. Grasshopper is “a graphical algorithm editor tightly integrated with Rhino’s 3-D modeling tools” (Davidson, 2023). Within Grasshopper, a closed polysurface is considered a *boundary representation*, a term which in this context refers to a data representation of a physically solid object. For Grasshopper, a boundary representation is considered as being composed of one or more mathematically modeled surfaces which are in turn represented by their bounding edges and vertices. Because the surfaces are joined at their edges, they collectively establish a boundary between the represented object’s interior and its exterior, hence the term *boundary representation* (Requicha 1980; Mantyla and Sulonen 1982). To the extent that the boundary representations, or “b-reps,” are unambiguous representations of solids, “any query whose answer depends solely on geometry and related attributes can in principle be answered” (Miller 1989). Thus, we depend on b-reps as the basic mechanism for computing volumes of entities representing building materials. However, because it is possible for b-reps to have a calculable volume equal to zero, for example in the case of an “open” b-rep such as a rectangular, planar surface, we distinguish b-reps with nonzero volume as “volume-compliant” b-reps.

Approaches to teaching Grasshopper in the context of architectural education continue to be debated, and their effectiveness questioned (Senske 2017). When the question is framed more generally in terms of teaching computer programming to architects, the debate assumes historical dimensions (Wurzer et al. 2011; Burry 1997; Schon 1988; Negroponete 1975). We chose to approach Grasshopper instruction through a conversational, question-answer format, which we attempt to summarize here.

We begin by diagramming, in a simple linear form, what we would like Grasshopper to do:

Next, we consider the meaning of “take all the stuff in the model” relative to how the software represents physical solids. In light of the background material on b-reps in the preceding section, what we mean is something more like this:

We can be somewhat more precise:

If we wish to visualize the combined volumes as a cube, we need to provide a specific instruction:

Considering that Grasshopper demands a step-by-step algorithmic formulation, we look again at making our procedure more specific.

And we can go one step more.

We discuss all of this preliminary work with students before Grasshopper is opened.

The next step involves “translating” our linear diagram into specific Grasshopper components and connections. To the extent possible, we present Grasshopper components in terms of comparable Rhino commands. For example, Rhino’s VOLUME command returns the calculated volume of a closed polysurface, and Grasshopper’s Volume component provides the same with respect to one or more b-reps.

The Grasshopper definition (Fig. 3) is introduced to students from a blank canvas, with each component inserted and connected to parallel the diagrammatic process just discussed.

Fig. 3. Grasshopper definition.

Grasshopper's Brep container, at the far left of Fig. 3, is used to designate one or more b-reps from the Rhino model. The Volume component calculates the volume of the designated b-reps. The Mass Addition component provides the total volume of all b-reps referenced by the container. The result, when raised to the power of one-third (1/3), is the cube root of the calculated total, i. e., that number which when cubed will equal the total. It remains only to construct a cube using the cube root as a side length, which is done with a Rectangle component and a Rectangular Box component. (Other methods are possible, e. g., an Extrude Curve component could be used to extrude a cube from the rectangular curve).

Example

To illustrate the use of the Grasshopper definition, we tested a Rhino model of Nolte Center (Fig. 4). The model was organized into layers corresponding to building materials including concrete, brick, and stone.

Fig. 4. From top: Concrete, brick, and stone in Nolte Center. Cubic-volume equivalents appear on the right.

Using the Grasshopper definition, and proceeding one layer at a time, the total volume of objects in each successive layer is calculated. Cubes are constructed corresponding to the calculated volumes. Finally, the cubes are reorganized on a plane for graphic comparison (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Material cubes in proportion to their quantities in the Rhino model.

Table 1 summarizes the calculations of simulated material weight in the Rhino model of Nolte Center.

simulated material in Rhino model	cubic feet	approximate material weight (pounds per cubic foot)	totals (pounds)
concrete	152,786	150	22,917,964
brick	39,317	120	4,718,034
stone	2,449	150	367,394
wood	1,096	45	49,312
terrazzo	222	110	24,450
steel	134	500	67,210
glass	51	150	7,725
			28,144,363

Discussion

By limiting consideration to what appears in the digital model, we exempt students from having to directly account for embodied carbon associated with factors such as extraction, processing, or transportation of building materials. Rather than serving as a precise calculator, the exercise operates as a prompt for awareness and as a potential tool for comparison of alternatives.

We are left with several questions for our future work. Pedagogically, we are interested in whether a method involving concentrated individual focus on single issues, in combination with peer-to-peer teaching, could lead to some form of effective cognitive diversity. Specifically from the perspective of embodied carbon, we are interested in measuring impacts of our approach on students' awareness and understanding, and especially on their design decision-making processes.

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